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ABSTRACT

This report presents the summary of the scientific and technical discussions in the ARIES WP7 Task 7.2 on Injection and Injection Subsystems for ring with Ultra-Low emittance. The development of such rings is strongly influenced by the apertures available for the beam (dynamic and momentum apertures) and by the capabilities of the injection systems to allow an efficient and transparent capture of the injected beam. Advances in these topics have in fact open the route to ever more aggressive lattice designs, hence reducing the equilibrium emittance to tens of pm. The corresponding technological challenges, in terms of kickers and pulsers were also extensively discussed and no serious showstopper was identified.

ARIES Consortium, 2019

For more information on ARIES, its partners and contributors please see <http://aries.web.cern.ch>

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Executive summary

Efficient and transparent injection in ultra-low emittance rings is a key component for the successful design and operation of such rings. In the past years a wealth of novel injection schemes were proposed and the corresponding technological challenges have been explored. As a result, new more aggressive upgrade projects have opted for ambitious injection schemes based on on-axis or swap-out, which do not require large dynamic apertures or nonlinear kickers and anti-septa which relax such demands. The Deliverable 7.2 consists in the report of the main activities and discussions held in the corresponding workshops.

1. Introduction

The injection process in ultra-low emittance damping rings and light sources has posed increasingly tighter demands on the injector systems and the associated technologies. The physics motivation have been different:

- damping rings require fast kickers for multibunch injection as a consequence of the downstream accelerator chain, bunch pattern and repetition rates required
- light sources need a transparent top-up injection and, more recently, they faced the problem of injection in rings with very small dynamic and momentum apertures.

It is interesting to note that novel on-axis injection schemes allow another technological jump in the landscape of quasi-diffraction limited light sources as shown in Fig. 1.1. Although the main step (red dots) is related to the introduction of the Multi-Bend-Achromats (MBA) lattices, the additional step forward enabled by new injection schemes is clear and has been proposed in all most ambitious projects (cyan dots). It is also clear that light sources play a preponderant role in these developments

This leap in emittance is underpinned by the development of variety of new beam physics ideas, by technological advance in the design of kickers and striplines and, equally important, in the development of new pulsed power modulators. These three major aspects have been the topics of Task 7.2 in ARIES WP7 (Rings for Ultra-Low Emittance - RUL ϵ). WP7 has supported networking activities and several workshops, two of which specifically dedicated to the discussion of injection schemes and injection subsystems, held in

- BESSY-II, August 2017 [1]
- PSI, April 2019 [2]

Despite the seemingly narrow technology scope, these workshops have been very well attended (50 and ~40 delegates respectively). The discussions have highlighted the cross disciplinarity of the themes, spanning beam physics, pulsed magnet and RF engineering, pulsed power supply, complex numerical simulations of the time dependent electromagnetic, mechanical and thermal properties of the injection systems.

Fig. 1.1: Survey of low emittance rings. The emittance over the square of the relativistic factor (ϵ_x/γ^2) is a measure of the aggressiveness of the lattice design. The circumference is a rough indication of the number of bending magnets accommodated in the ring [8]

The present report is a summary of the most recent developments in the field and of the main points discussed in the ARIES WP7 Task. 7.2 workshops. These include new injection schemes, kicker/stripline developments and pulser technology.

2. Injection schemes for ultra-low emittance rings

Injection in ultra-low emittance rings is notoriously difficult due to the restricted apertures (both dynamics and momentum apertures, i.e. on-momentum and off-momentum). In fact, the optimisation of the apertures is the key problem in the design of ultra-low emittance rings. While old rings based on standard double-bend or triple-bend achromats (DBA or TBA) inject comfortably in 10-15 mm Dynamic Aperture (DA) and 3-4% momentum aperture, ultra-low emittance rings hardly achieve such values. Such apertures are unlikely to be available in the new rings and, as a consequence, the old injection schemes based on the four (or three) kickers closed orbit bumps are not attractive solutions. In fact as shown in Fig. 2.1, such injection scheme requires a separation of the injected beam to the stored beam given at least by

- some rms beam size of the injected beam
- septum thickness
- rms beam size of the stored beam

To these values, one should add the design separation of the trajectories of the stored beam and the injected beam, as given by the geometric layout of the injection scheme.

Fig. 2.1: Four kickers closed orbit bump injection scheme. The dimension are the one of Diamond injection straight

A possible reduction of the distance between stored beam and injected beam requires therefore a smaller injected beam size, a smaller septum thickness and smaller separation of the trajectories. Each of these aspects can be tackled separately. In fact small emittance boosters have been introduced, e.g. at SLS (9nm) and ALBA (3 nm) locating them in the same tunnel as the main ring. Thinner septa can be conceived, although electrostatic septa – which normally can be made 100 μm thin – do not seem to provide the required kicks (few mrad). A reduction of the distance

between the trajectory of the injected beam and the stored beam can be achieved using a so-called anti-septum as proposed in the CDR of the SLS 2.0 upgrade [20]. The idea is to build kicker 3 of Fig. 2.1 with a magnetic channel that shields the pulsed field, hence allowing a closer approach of the trajectory of the injected beam to the stored beam. Fig. 2.2 shows a possible trajectory layout.

Fig. 2.2: Trajectories of the injected and stored beam with an anti-septum scheme. The dimensions are the one of Diamond II proposed injection scheme [11]

The SLS. 2.0 CDR reports that an efficient injection can be reached with less than 5 mm dynamic apertures. It is worthwhile stressing that this injection scheme, although based on well established concepts, has never been tried, and injection in such small dynamic aperture remains a potential R&D area.

The off axis injection scheme based on several kickers suffers however from a significant operational problem due to the perturbation they induce in the stored beam. The perturbation is due to the difficulty in achieving a perfectly closed orbit bump during injection and the consequent stored beam oscillations which persist for a few transverse damping time. In many cases these are completely unacceptable for the operation of the experiments. A global survey of the injection transient problem was carried out during the first topical workshop [1] showing that no machine can actually claim better than $\sim 100 \mu\text{m}$ peak-to-peak residual oscillations during injection. The difficulty in achieving a closed orbit bump are traced down to the difficulty of achieving exactly identical magnetic field pulses with four different kickers. Difficulty with coating uniformity and homogeneity are suspected to be the root cause of this problem, but thorough and conclusive experimental evidence is still lacking. Even series powering of the kicker magnets has not proven to solve the issue, so much that there is now a significant agreement in the community that a perfect closure is beyond the practical capabilities of such system.

As a result, a new line of R&D has gain relevance in the past years, based on the non-linear kicker (NLK) concept. The NLK is a pulsed magnet that provides a highly nonlinear magnetic field as shown in Fig. 2.3, such that the field at the centre is zero and it grows nonlinearly, in an octupole-like fashion, in the horizontal plane. In this way the stored beam, at the centre of the aperture does not experience any kick, while the injected beam, entering at the side (few mm) is kicked inside the dynamic aperture, provided the phase advance between septum and NLK are properly adjusted.

Fig. 2.3: Transverse dependence of the magnetic field in a NLK. Example taken from SOLEIL's NLK [4]

The original design proposed by BESSY-II [8] was built and installed in the ring in 2011. The first incarnation of the NLK suffered from serious heating issues. The design was modified to have a better Ti coating and to power the four wires in series. The performance improved guaranteeing 80 % injection efficiency with minimal perturbation of the stored beam as reported in Fig. 2.4.

Fig. 2.4: BESSY-II results without (left) with (right) the injection kicker perturbation [17]

The BESSY II design was subsequently taken over by SOLEIL who built a NLK for the MAX IV ring. Modification of the support structure, removing any metallic (SS) part helped with the reliability of the pulsing. However, significant difficulties were met in the precise positioning of the wires. It turns out that machining of a sapphire chamber to the required tolerance ($< 20 \mu\text{m}$) was a source of significant difficulties for the manufacturer and eventually delayed the NLK

construction project. A noncompliant version of the NLK was installed in the MAX IV ring and proved however to be a success. Fig. 2.5 shows the reduction of the injection transient.

Fig. 2.5: Reduction of transient with MAX IV kicker [5]

The NLK is now routinely used for operation at MAX IV. A new version is under construction by SOLEIL which also plans to install it for standard routine operation. The experience cumulated with these studies highlighted a number of technical difficulties associated with the NLK. Firstly, the construction tolerances are at the limit of the present machining technology with ceramics. Secondly, for machines that require a kick closer to the centre of the aperture, the NLK design must have a small vertical aperture, creating concerns for the operation of such fixed gap system in a ring. The requirement on the vertical aperture can be relaxed assuming that the injected beam is not necessarily kicked at the top of the magnetic field but during the slope. However, operating in these conditions poses tighter requirements on the pulser, and on the emittance of the injected beam which can be significantly smeared by the non-uniform kick received in the magnetic field slope of the NLK. It is generally accepted that such system are not easy to build and, in any case, they still require a significant transverse dynamic aperture of a few mm.

For these reasons, a new series of injection schemes have been developed in the last years, based on more or less exotic variants of the concept of on-axis injection. Two strands can be immediately separated here. The on-axis injection allows accumulation or it is a swap-out injection where the existing beam is kicked out and fully replaced by a new incoming fresh beam. As before, the main issues to consider are a good injection efficiency and a transparent top-up.

On-axis injection with accumulation is achieved in the so called longitudinal injection schemes, where the injected beam is timed to enter the ring in between the stored bunches and kicked on axis, by using the golf club acceptance (requires off-energy injection) or by a NLK (requires off-energy injection and large dispersion at the injection point). In both cases a fast kicker is required, capable of delivering enough kick to capture the injected beam and fast enough to disappear before the following bunch arrives, so as not to kick out or disturb the stored beam. In a machine operating with 500 MHz this would mean a zero-to-zero pulse duration of less than 4 ns (kicking only one bunch). In a 100 MHz machine, this time interval relaxes to 20 ns. Where possible this scheme could work well for those machine which operate with fill pattern that allow a bunch separation of

10 ns or more. It is evident in any case that these schemes are enabled by the development of fast kicker and pulsers.

An example of on-axis accumulation using off energy injection in the golf club longitudinal acceptance is shown in Fig. 2.6 and Fig. 2.7

Fig. 2.6: layout of the longitudinal off-energy injection scheme [3]

Fig. 2.7; golf club acceptance and injection [7]

On-axis injection with swap-out [12] is conceptually very simple in that it requires simply a fast kicker to drive the stored beam out and inject the new fresh beam on-axis. Such scheme however must consider the amount of charge that needs swapping out and the rate. Delivering the amount of charge present in the stored beam requires a high charge injector which can deal with pulses on the order of 10 nC or more. If a multi-bunch injection is used to relax the top-up repetition rate, we should consider that the injected bunches (with the injector emittance much larger than the main ring) will effectively create a loss of brightness for a few damping times. This aspect defeats the idea of transparent injection.

Many other novel injection schemes have been proposed and we defer to the summaries of the workshop [1] and [2] for an extensive review. Here we want to highlight an interesting combination of the two ideas (off-axis and on-axis injection) whereby the longitudinal on-axis injection is eased by an upstream injection stage provided by an off-axis scheme based on anti-septum [6] or NLK. In this way, the high voltage requirements on the fast kicker can be relaxed,

although still maintaining the request of ultra-short pulse. The location of the kicker should be such that the injected trajectory crosses the reference orbit as shown in Fig. 2.8

Fig. 2.8: Injection trajectory in a combined anti-septum and HV fast kicker injection [6]

This injection scheme will inject only one bunch, allowing a much reduced transient, provided the kicker is faster than the intra-bunch spacing (2 ns at 500 MHz). Further variants can be devised as the pictorial view show in Fig. 2.9. If we allow more than one bunch to be hit by the kicker pulse, we can relax the request on the pulse peak voltage as long as the neighbouring bunches are not kicked out by the tails in the pulse. If sufficient DA is available a single kicker injection scheme can be devised (Fig. 2.9 bottom). This scheme will not require an off time injection.

Fig. 2.9: Timing of longitudinal injection schemes aided by an anti-septum: (top) standard on-axis scheme, (middle) standard on-axis scheme with relaxed pulse duration, (bottom) share DA injection [6]

3. Kicker magnets and striplines

Magnetic kickers ferrite based do not seem to provide fast enough kick to satisfy the requirement of few ns rise-fall time and they have been used only fast compensation kicker with significantly longer pulses [16]. As an example, SPring-8 has used three compensation kickers (see Fig. 3.1) to compensate the differences in the pulses of the four kickers closed orbit bump at different times (see Fig. 3.2).

Fig. 3.1: three Fast Compensation Kickers (FCK) used at Spring-8 [16]

Fig. 3.2: parts of the main kicker pulse targeted for compensation [16]

In general, stripline kickers design are preferred. The initial studies for CLIC damping ring were meant to focus on providing 12.5 kV pulses with fast rise and fall time (100 ns) and relatively long flat top (variable from 160 ns to 900 ns), as shown in Fig. 3.3.

Fig. 3.3: test of inductive adders prototype pulses for the CLIC damping ring [13]

Supported by the ARIES WP7, prototyping and experimental tests of such striplines driven by inductive adders have been made at ALBA. Both pulser and stripline were temporarily installed in the ALBA straight section as shown in Fig. 3.4 and Fig. 3.5. As it was seen that long cables distort the pulse, the inductive adders were installed in the tunnel as close as possible to the stripline kickers and were removed after the test. The main parameters of the CLIC damping ring kickers are reported in Tab. 3.1

Fig. 3.4: CLIC damping ring stripline kicker installed at ALBA

Fig. 3.5: inductive adders installed in the tunnel close the stripline

Tab. 3.1: CLIC stripline parameters

Kick angle,mrad	1.5
Effective length, m	1.7
Good Field Region, mm	± 1
Field homogeneity	$\pm 2 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Flat top reproducibility	$\pm 1 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Pulse rise & fall time, ns	100
Pulse flat top, ns	160 - 900

While initial tests were unsuccessful due to strong outgassing of the ceramic MACOR supports of the striplines hit by synchrotron radiation as shown in Fig. 3.6, recent tests were more promising and a full characterisation of the kicker is ongoing.

SR hitting the MACOR rings

Fig. 3.6: MACOR support holding the stripline damaged by synchrotron radiation [13]

Striplines are proposed in basically all swap-out injection schemes (APS-U, ALS-U, HEPS, PETRA IV). The main design issue for such striplines is in achieving the desired kick minimizing the driving voltage: this requires that the blades of the stripline are placed as close as feasible. For practical reasons, it is also advisable to keep the impedance of the stripline in the operating mode (common mode) to 50 Ohm. The ALS-U design is reported in Fig. 3.7. The distance between the blades is only 6 mm. Such striplines are meant to be fed by 5.25 kV pulses with a flat top of 50 ns and rise-fall time of 7 ns with a flat top ripple of less than 1%.

Fig. 3.7: ALS-U stripline cross section [10]

A major difficulty in the design of the striplines is in the minimisation of the impedance seen by the beam. For these reasons a tapered design of the entry and exit section is proposed. Detailed studies are carried out at several labs and an example of the DAFNE stripline kicker is reported in Fig. 3.8. The corresponding improvement in the transverse impedance is reported in Fig. 3.9

Fig. 3.8: tapered stripline design (left) proposed at DAFNE and untapered design (right) [6]

Fig. 3.9: Impedance of DAFNE striplines with and without tapers [5]

DAFNE fast striplines are meant to provide 45 kV in 5 ns zero-to-zero pulses as shown in Fig. 3.10. However, the reliability of such pulser is still poor and further R&D is in progress.

Fig. 3.10: Measured DAFNE stripline kicker pulses [5]

4. HV fast pulsers

Essential to the success of the system is the availability of a fast pulsers that can deliver high voltages with fast rise/fall time. The design of the pulser assumes a 50 Ohm load and fast pulses are achieved with capacitive energy storage and thyratrons switches. Variants of this scheme, like inductive adders are popular and have been proposed for CLIC damping rings and for HEPS. It has to be noted that many synchrotron light sources operate with short bunch spacing (2 ns at 500 MHz) therefore they would ideally aim at rise/fall time less than the bunch spacing (~ 1 ns). These seem to be still outside of the present capabilities of fast pulsers.

The R&D effort so far has targeted fast rise-fall times and long flat-top, however single bunch swap out would not necessarily need a flat-top pulse. Gaussian pulses are easier to achieve and several laboratories and industries have active R&D programmes. As an example, HEPS has developed pulser based on an inductive adders switched by a drift step recovery diode (DSRD) to generate 17.4 kV in 4 ns pulses as shown in Fig. 4.1. Reliability tests for continuous operation 8 hours every day of 15 kV-15ns pulses at a repetition rate of 300 Hz were carried out for 4 weeks without problems.

Figure 4.1: fast kicker pulses at HEPS with inductive adders and DSRD [9]

Another interesting example is given by a commercial company [15] with pulser delivering 4 ns Gaussian pulses zero-to-zero 10 kV that can be pushed to 3-5 kV in 2 ns zero-to-zero pulses (see Fig. 4.2), similar to the results reported by HEPS. Sydora pulsers are based on MOSFET switches.

Fig. 4.2: Sydora pulser output with 2 ns Gaussian pulses of 3 kV peak voltage [15]

5. Future plans / Conclusion / relation to other ARIES work

ARIES WP7 Task. 7.2 has tackled one of the major issues in the development of ultra low emittance rings, consisting in the efficient and transparent injection in such small aperture rings. Small dynamic and momentum apertures are an intrinsic characteristic of such rings due to the strong focussing required to reduce the equilibrium emittance. Despite the great effort spent in the optimisation of the nonlinear beam dynamics, it appears that DA of a few mm only can be reached. These difficulties have prompted a new approach to the injection problem where the injection system is designed specifically to inject in small apertures: a large number of novel injection schemes have been proposed and reviewed in two topical workshops organised by ARIES WP7. These have given the possibility to discuss also the technological issues associated with the design of the striplines and the pulser driving the injection elements.

ARIES WP7 in Task 4.4 has also fostered a number of beam tests towards the commissioning and operation of ultra-low emittance rings dealing specifically with injection issues Two machine shifts were performed at the BESSY-II synchrotron on 17th and 18th of June 2018 in addition to further beam time on 13th of February and 25th June 2018. The main team consisted of Peter Kuske, Ji Li (HZB) and Masamitsu Aiba (PSI).

The activity of the WP7 Task 4.2 will continue by promoting further networking activities to answer the questions left open and to provide support to the new design projects and to the commissioning of the upcoming rings ESRF-EBS [18] and Sirius [19] planned for 2020.

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7. Annex: Glossary

Acronym	Definition
CDR	Conceptual Design Report
DA	Dynamic Aperture
DBA	Double-Bend Achromats
NLK	Non-Linear Kicker
TBA	Triple-Bend Achromats